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THE CONSUMER TRENDS OF SECONDHAND CLOTHING IN YOUNG PEOPLE – THE CASE OF THE GENERATION Z OF VIETNAM

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, secondhand clothes have become a fashion trend that is enthusiastically supported by Vietnamese youth thanks to their fashionability and environmental friendliness. A series of second-hand shops, warehouses, and consignment events have sprung up in parallel with second-hand markets that have existed for many years, still attracting many visitors. In order to examine the trend of secondhand clothing consumption among young Vietnamese, the research team conducted this study. Through the results of the study, it can be seen that the main personal factors leading to the use of secondhand clothes by the survey subjects are spending savings and personal preferences. Most of the decisions to buy secondhand clothes are influenced by the uniqueness of the product and by friends and relatives. The most enabling aspect when using secondhand clothes is the product quality and the product's design, while the aspects that are the most concerns by both users and non-users of secondhand clothes are a matter of hygiene and health.

KEYWORDS

Trends; Consumer trends; Secondhand Clothes; Vietnamese young people; GenerationZ.

1. Identify the issue

The textile industry is currently the second most polluting one in the world, accounting for 10% of carbon emissions and 20% of global waste water (Pal & Gander, 2018). In Spain, each person discards 7kg of clothing per year, generating a total of 326,000 tons of clothing waste annually (Vinces et al., 2020). According to the World Wildlife Fund (WWF), each year the global fashion industry consumes about 1.5 billion liters of water, creating 92 million tons of waste. While cotton cultivation accounts for only 2.4% of arable land world wide, it uses up to 10% of industry-wide chemicals and 25% of pesticides. Emissions of the textile industry account for 2-10% of the total greenhouse gas emissions and increase to 26% by 2050 if the industry does not make changes (Ha Van, 2021).

Facing this situation, the textile industry needs to make changes in production, process, and product properties. Along with that, trends, and consumer intentions also play an important role. Research by Joy et al (2012); Zamani et al (2017) point out that the low prices of fast fashion motivate consumers to buy new clothes frequently, resulting in a large amount of clothing that goes unused and becomes waste.

In Vietnam, according to a survey report by YouGov (2017), in 2016, 75% of adult Vietnamese consumers give up or throw away clothes, most of which are used only once. It can be seen that the consumer factor influences the level of environmental pollution in the textile industry. Along with the current trend, consumers have been increasingly aware of environmental protection, and the trend of using secondhand clothes has become more and more popular.

In this study, we will examine the trend of secondhand clothing consumption by Vietnamese young people of Generation Z (born 1995-2010). Through the review process, the group concluded the consumption trends that have been synthesized by previous studies and conducted a survey in April 2023 to identify and evaluate those consumer trends through survey results. From there, the research team offers some managerial implications for secondhand clothes sellers to be able to grasp the trend of green consumption and better meet the green consumption needs of consumers.

2. Overview of secondhand clothes

2.1. Secondhand clothing notion

When it comes to secondhand clothes, we can simply understand the clothes that have been used or owned by a person before. (Yang & et al 2017)

In addition, standing at different angles, there are also different concepts of secondhand clothes

From an economic point of view, used clothing is clothing that has been used before and is somehow returned to circulation in the next consumption cycle and often has the incentive to purchase. With lower prices. (Carrigan et al., 2013)

From a psychological standpoint, secondhand clothes are considered to be unique and distinctive, there by expressing the personality of the wearer (Roux and Guiot, 2008; Gullstrand et al., 2016). Clothing, whether new or used, is a product through which the wearer expresses a sense of self to those around him and creates his or her own identity (Belk, 1988). term of social norms (Thompson and Haytko, 1997). With this understanding, the factor to distinguish from new clothes is that secondhand clothes have a fashion style that satisfies the desire to express the ego of consumers through these products.

From a social-moral perspective, secondhand clothes help reduce waste in the environment, besides, buying secondhand clothes is also a way to help consumers openly protest against consumerism. and the expansion of fast fashion brands in the world towards fair trade. (Mintel, 2009)

2.2. Secondhand clothes' characteristics

According to Hoa, B.T.P (2021) secondhand clothes are a very special product; it contains a lot of value. Collectively, they have the following characteristics:

- Is clothing that has been previously purchased (owned by the consumer);
- These clothes may have been used before, or it has never been used but have only been purchased (owned by the consumer);
- These clothes are sold for less than new clothes;
- These clothes are manufactured by a certain brand and may be a product of a well-known brand;
- These clothes are unique and different;
- Their quality is still good, even like new;
- Are environmentally friendly products that reduce waste from clothing.

2.3. Factors affecting young people's tendency to consume secondhand clothes

Research by Styvén and Mariani (2020) indicates that there are 3 main factors affecting consumers' attitudes towards buying secondhand clothes: Perception of sustainability; Economic engine; and Distance to the consumer system. In which, perception of sustainability and economic motivation has a positive impact on consumers' attitudes towards buying secondhand clothes. In addition, the distance factor to the consumption system has a reciprocal effect on consumer attitudes.

Many empirical studies have shown consumers' motivation to buy secondhand clothes. Gwozdz et al (2014); Joung & Park (2013); Kim & Damhorst (1998) show that the intention to buy secondhand clothes is rooted in economic motivation. Research by Brace-Govan and Binay (2010); Cervillon et al (2012); Guiot and Roux (2010); Roux & Korchia (2006) point out moral motives and social concerns. In addition, several other studies have shown that fashion dynamics and the uniqueness of secondhand clothes affect consumers' usage trends such as Beard (2008); DeLong et al (2005); Ferraro et al (2016); Gregson et al (2002).

Buying secondhand clothes is a measure to protect the environment, against the phenomenon of throwing clothes into the environment and the trend of using single-use clothes causing waste and environmental pollution (Carrigan et al., 2013; Roux & Korchia, 2006; Vines et al, 2020).

Besides, many empirical studies also show that the motivation affecting consumers' buying behavior of secondhand clothes is originality or exclusivity. People always pursue trends, individuality, and stand out from the crowd by using unique products (Brace – Govan & Binay, 2010; Palmer, 2005).

According to Burns & Waren (1995), how to express the uniqueness of each person through the clothes they wear. In addition, when wearing unique costumes, people will stand out in the crowd and get attention from people around them (Cervillon et al., 2012; Hansen, 200

Used clothing is the optimal choice for consumers before this engine because secondhand clothes are not available in the same volume, size, or style as new products. Especially "limited" clothes, ie only produced in a certain quantity. Most of the empirical studies indicate the motivations that influence the intention to buy used clothing but have only explored the motives in isolation. Research by Hoa, B.T.P (2021) on the motivation of Vietnamese people to buy secondhand clothes. The research results show that 8 motives have an impact on consumer's intention to buy secondhand clothes: Price motive; Desired motives for a fair price; Fashion engine; The motive of originality; Recreational engine; Motivation for social communication; Eco-ethical motives; Criticism motive.

- External factors affecting the purchase of secondhand clothes are considered in the following aspects: The uniqueness of the product, the influence of friends and relatives, the influence of Kols fashion, and the influence of product marketing and promotion.

- Aspects to be considered when buying secondhand clothes: Origin, price, environmental friendliness.

- Benefits of using secondhand clothes.

- Concerns about using secondhand clothes.

- In addition, this study also considers the content related to the used clothing shopping channel, the frequency of use, the amount of money young people are willing to pay to buy secondhand clothes...

3. Research Methodology

To study "The trend of young people to use secondhand clothes - The case of Generation Z in Vietnam", the research team used 2 research methods including desk research (reviewing documents has been published in the media) and a sociological survey (collecting answers sheets from young generation Z born in 1995-2010 in Vietnam). The data will be aggregated and analyzed using Excel software.

Using the desk research method, the research team reviewed the literature on used clothing consumption trends and used clothing consumption trend reports published in the media, communication, and research at home and abroad. The research team developed a survey form to conduct a sociological investigation on the trend of used clothing consumption among young people of Generation Z in Vietnam.

The data collection method conducted by the research team is based on two methods: the convenience sampling method and the "snowball" method - the method of finding the next object based on suggestions or recommendations. of the surveyed subjects. The survey was built on Google Driver, conducted a test interview with 5 young people who often use secondhand clothes to complete the survey and send the survey link (<http://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScZ52Sr3mJ1Zj-MHp1uzg7HVLf1pu7KWdgpFrhWK1BdEhvpQ/viewform>) to young Vietnamese generation Z through social media such as Facebook, Zalo, Email... The total number of survey votes collected is 323 votes. The survey data was synthesized and statistical using Excel software, from which to analyze and demonstrate the research problem.

In addition, the research team conducted in-depth interviews with 4 sellers of used clothing products and 9 young people with the role of customers, consumers, and fashionistas to supplement the bases for this part. discuss.

4. Survey Results

4.1. Characteristics of the survey participants

Figure 1. Gender of survey participants

Source: The survey results

With the number of 323 people participating in the survey, there are 226 female friends (accounting for 70%), 87 male friends (accounting for 26.9%), and 10 people who do not want to be specific (accounting for 3.1%).

Figure 2. Age of survey participants

Source: The survey results

Of the 323 survey participants, 150 were high school students (accounting for 46.4%), 148 were university students (accounting for 45.8%) and 25 were employed (accounting for 7.7%).

Figure 3. Living area of survey participants

Source: The survey results

With 323 survey participants, 217 people live in urban areas (accounting for 67.2%) and 106 people live in rural areas (accounting for 32.8%).

4.2. Consumption trend of secondhand clothes of Vietnamese youth - Generation Z

The survey results recorded that nearly 68% of the survey participants used secondhand clothes.

Figure 4. Number of survey respondents using secondhand clothes

Source: The survey results

Survey about ever / or never secondhand clothes. With 323 survey participants, **219 people used secondhand clothes (accounting for 68%), and 104 people did not use secondhand clothes, accounting for 32%**. Reasons for not using secondhand clothes are noted in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Reasons not to use secondhand clothes

Source: The survey results

Of the 104 survey participants who did not use secondhand clothes, 28 people chose the reason "It is difficult to choose the right size of clothes" (accounting for 26.9%), 46 people chose the reason "Simple not like" (accounting for 44.2%), 40 people chose the reason "Concerned about product origin" (accounting for 38.5%), **64 people chose the reason as "Fear about hygiene/health issues" (61.5%) accounted for the highest percentage**, 18 people chose the reason "time-consuming to choose" (17.3%), 8 people chose the reason "not many people use it" (accounting for 7.7%) and 15 people chose "Other" (14.4%).

Figure 6. The future trend of buying secondhand clothes of consumers who do not currently use secondhand clothes

Source: The survey results

With 104 survey respondents currently not using secondhand clothes, when surveying them about buying/using secondhand clothes in the future. With the convention of point 1. Still do not buy/use

(17 people); 2. May still not buy/use (17 people); 3. Neutral (23 people); 4. Can buy/use (43 people); 5. Will buy and use (4 people) The average score, in this case, is 3.19 points, which that shows that out of 104 survey participants, the average score shows that those **who are not currently using secondhand clothes have a "neutral" attitude about buying secondhand clothes in the future.**

Figure 7. Time to start using secondhand clothes of survey participants

Source: The survey results

With 219 survey participants using secondhand clothes, 149 people used it a long time ago (accounting for 68%), and 70 people used it recently (accounting for 32%).

Figure 8. Frequency of using secondhand clothes by survey participants

Source: The survey results

With 219 survey participants using secondhand clothes, with convention 1. Rarely used (49 people); 2. Sometimes used (131 people) and 3 often used (39 people). The average score, in this case, is 1.95 points, indicating the frequency of using secondhand clothes by the survey respondents at the level of **“Sometimes” using used clothing products.**

Figure 9. Percentage of used items in survey respondents' closets

Source: The survey results

With 219 survey participants using secondhand clothes, **mostly used items account for less than 10% of their wardrobe (100 people - 45.7%)**, the number of respondents from 10 to 30 % (79 people - 36.1%), from 30 - 50% (27 people - 12.3%), from 50 - 70% (8 people - 3.7%), over 70% only 5 people (2,3%).

Figure 10. The level of use of secondhand clothes by people around the survey subject

Source: The survey results

With 219 survey participants who used secondhand clothes, the assessment of the level of used clothing use of people around the survey subjects was with convention 1. Very few (17 people - 7.8%); 2. Few (51 people – 23.3%); 3. Normal (131 people – 59.8%); 4. Many (17 people – 7.8%); 5. So many (3 people – 1.4%). The average score of 2.71 points shows that **people around the survey subject use secondhand clothes at a "Normal" level.**

Figure 11. Channel to buy secondhand clothes of survey subjects

Source: The survey results

With 219 survey participants using secondhand clothes, **119 people bought at stores** (accounting for 54.3%, accounting for the highest percentage), 77 people bought from friends (accounting for 35.2%), groups, relatives, given...

Figure 12. Trends in buying secondhand clothes online of survey respondents

Source: The survey results

With 219 survey participants using secondhand clothes, 107 people do not use online channels to buy secondhand clothes (accounting for 48.9%), **112 people use online channels to buy secondhand clothes (accounting for 51.1%)**, showing that online shopping in general, shopping for secondhand clothes is also interested by young people.

Figure 13. Online shopping channel for secondhand clothes of survey subjects

Source: The survey results

With 112 survey respondents shopping for secondhand clothes online, it shows that **Instagram is the most popular shopping channel for 57 people (50.9%)** followed by Facebook 54 people (48.2%), TikTok is 34 people (30.4%), in addition to other shopping channels like Shopee...

Figure 14. About the income level of the survey participants

The survey results show that the income/subsidy level from the family of the survey respondents is **mainly below 500,000 VND (84 people)**, followed by 500,000 VND to less than 1 million VND (58 people), from 1 to 2 million dong (27 people), from 2 to 5 million dong (26 people) and over 5 million dong is 20 people.

Also according to the survey results, the amount of money that the respondents **are willing to pay for secondhand clothes is mostly less than 200,000 VND a month (124 people - 57%)**.

Figure 15. Amount willing to pay to buy secondhand clothes

Source: The survey results

The number of people willing to pay from 200 to 400 thousand VND is 57 people (26%), from 400 to 800,000 VND is 23 people (10%), from 800 to 1 million VND is 9 people (4%), the number of people willing to pay the amount from 1 million or more is very few.

Figure 16. Personal factors influence the decision to buy secondhandclothes

Source: The survey results

Regarding personal factors affecting the decision to buy secondhand clothes, the survey results found that **the biggest reason here is “Due to savings in spending”** 128 people (58.4%) followed by “Personal preferences” 123 people (56.2%), third place is due to “Following the trend of being environmentally friendly” 71 people (32.4%), followed by “Due to economic conditions” 69 people (31.5%), “Create your fashion style” 63 people (28.8%), by “Favoring classic fashion style” 59 people (26.9%), In addition, the survey also recorded some other reasons such as strange problems, not being identical to anyone, due to being given as a gift, etc.

Figure 17. External factors influence the decision to buy secondhand clothes

Source: The survey results

Regarding the external factors affecting the decision to buy secondhand clothes, the factor with **the largest choice is “Influenced by the uniqueness of the product”** 118 people (53.9%), followed by “Due to the influence of friends and relatives” 102 people (46.6%), “Due to the influence of Kols's fashion style” 41 people (18.7%) and “Due to the influence of marketing and spreading the product widely” 46 people (21%), in addition, the survey recorded many other reasons such as because secondhand clothes, many new clothing products, diverse designs, beautiful products, do not overlap with other people's products...

Regarding the aspects consumers care about when buying secondhand clothes, the research team mentions 7 aspects, the results of the survey questions are designed according to the 5-level Likert scale in which: 1. Very disinterested; 2. Not interested; 3. Normal; 4. Concern; 5. Very interested.

Table 1. The aspects consumers care about when buying secondhand clothes

No	The aspect of interest	1. Very disinterested	2. Not interested	3. Normal	4. Concern	5. Very interested	Average point	Oder/ Interest level
1	Origin of products	8	15	103	59	34	3.44	6. Concern
2	The price of the product	8	3	53	100	55	3.87	3. Concern
3	Quality of the product	6	3	38	101	71	4.04	1. Concern
4	Designs and models of products	9	1	36	102	71	4.03	2. Concern
5	Promotions, discounts...	9	21	83	69	37	3.47	5. Concern
6	Environmental friendliness	8	15	90	73	33	3.49	4. Concern
7	Customer care	9	19	91	71	29	3.42	7. Concern

Source: The survey results

When calculating the average score of all aspects, the results show that the aspect that is the most interesting is **“Product quality”** 4.04 points, followed by **“Product design and model”** 4.03 points, 3rd place is the aspect of **“Price of the product”** with 3.87 points, the aspect of **“Environmental friendliness”** with 3.49 points, followed by **“Promotions and discounts”** 3, 47 points, **“Product origin”** 3.44 points and finally **“Customer care service”** 3.42 points.

Figure 18. In terms of concern when buying secondhand clothes

Source: The survey results

Figure 19. Benefits of using secondhand clothes

Source: The survey results

The survey results show that **the biggest benefit according to the respondents' assessment of using secondhand clothes is "Cost saving" with 196 choices (89.5%)**, followed by **"Contributing to environmental protection" with 138 choices (63%)**, and using secondhand clothes will help **"Get a unique product" 101 choices (46.1%)**, in addition also help **"Express your style" 61 votes (27.9%)** ... However, the use of secondhand clothes also brings some concerns to users.

Figure 20. Concerns about using secondhand clothes

Source: The survey results

The biggest concern for people who use secondhand clothes is "Fear of hygiene and health problems" with 149 choices (68%), followed by **"Difficulty choosing the right size" with 126 choices (57.5%)**, **"Concern about product origin" with 99 choices (45.2%)**, **"Takes time to choose" 63 turns selection (28.8%)**, **"Not many people use secondhand clothes" 25 choices (11.4%)** and some other issues such as the newness of the product...

5. Discussion

Research results show that most young people have concerns about the use of secondhand clothes due to "Fear about hygiene/health issues", this is similar to the point of view made by Boardman, R., Zhou, Y., Guo, Y (2022), Hur (2020) and Camila (2018), Nemeroff, C. and Rozin, P. (1994), Goffman, E. (1971), Gregson, N. and Crewe, L. (2003). In-depth interviews with young people about the consumption of secondhand clothes also recorded some views on this issue. The first young person in the in-depth interview (NM1), said that *"...If I know the handling process, feel secure about hygiene, I will buy secondhand clothes..."* The third young person (NM3) thinks that *"...Wearing secondhand clothes, the feeling of enjoying the uniqueness of the product is reduced every time the thought of not knowing if the product is really clean"*. Meanwhile, in our in-depth interview with the seller, we received information shared from the seller about this issue, the first seller in the interview (NB1) said: *"...Of course, we have to protect our crafting skills as soon as possible before putting them up for sale. My son also arranges the shop in his style, not in a pile like in the market..."*, also the problem of hygiene of secondhand clothes second seller (NB2) said *"...After receiving the package, all of them are very clean and ready for sale. In addition, we also check the condition quite carefully when the condition is on the post when selling the product..."* For those who do not use secondhand clothes, they have a **"Neutral"** attitude to buying secondhand clothes in the future, so it is necessary to take measures to influence purchase intention so that these consumers see the benefits of the product. In particular, it is necessary to address their concerns with the product especially hygiene/health to promote the intention of these consumers to purchase the product. In this regard, according to the in-depth interview (NM3), this person who has never used a used clothing product said that *"... Will consider using the product, because now many of you are using it, many of the things you buy are unique..."*, but (NM5) said that *"...I won't buy it, because I don't know who used it before..."*.

*** Sellers need to take measures to make buyers feel secure about hygiene/health issues. Several photos and videos prove that the product has been processed and ensures cleanliness and safety.**

Regarding the personal factor, the survey recorded that buying secondhand clothes was the biggest reason *"Due to saving money"* and was also considered the most chosen benefit factor of consumers with secondhand clothes this is consistent with the study of Styvén and Mariani (2020), Gwozdz et al (2014); Joung & Park (2013); Kim & Damhorst (1998); Hoa, B.T.P (2021); Guiot, D. and Roux, D. (2010). There is no common price for secondhand clothes, only the seller's price for them. Regarding the price issue and the decision to buy the product, the fourth young person (NM4) in our in-depth interview said that *"...Price is a matter of great concern to me. The main reason for choosing to buy products is because of saving money and still having unique products..."*. Some young people in our interview also said that cheapness and bargaining are the issues you care about when buying products (NM6) *"...In my opinion, secondhand clothes are cheap and every secondhand only has one product, so I won't be able to match anyone..."* (buying because of its uniqueness), (NM8) *"...I often go to the market to buy secondhand clothes because I like the feeling of being hunted something beautiful, strange, but at a great price..."* (shopping experience), (NM9) *"...I buy secondhand because there are many rare items that have been around for a long time or are branded items that are quite cheap..."*

Regarding this issue, according to the results of the interview with the third seller (NB3), it is possible to set the price according to each product or selectively sell at the same price. With common sense, the same price will usually attract more viewers... *"With the fourth seller (NB4) in our in-depth*

interview said that"... "Can adjust the price a bit higher so that when people buy it, the price can be adjusted a little higher". If you buy with a bargain, I can reduce it accordingly..."

*** Depending on the level of old, new, and design, the seller needs to offer an appropriate price, have more experiences for customers, create a unique hunting mentality, and still get a bargain.**

The results also show that for those who use secondhand clothes, the frequency of use is only **"Occasionally"** and used items account for less than 10% of their wardrobe, the amount they are willing to pay mostly at less than 200,000 VND. Or, the opinion of the surveyed people is that **"Everyone around the survey subject uses secondhand clothes at a normal level"**. In our in-depth interview, it was noted that consumers are seeing the trend of 2hand clothing consumption gradually forming, the 7th young person (NM7) in our interview showed that *"...Walk... I just started buying secondhand clothes these days because my friends use them a lot..."* (influenced from friends and relatives).

In terms of shopping online channels. The survey results recorded that 51.1% of you buy clothes online, **and Instagram is the shopping channel chosen by many of them**, the result of the second in-depth interview with the second seller (NB2) also recorded this result. *"...Currently, my shop uses Instagram for marketing because this is a platform that young people often use and it's easy to exchange and buy things. In addition, we opened a TikTok channel, but we haven't invested much in content..."*. When the trend of online shopping is formed, especially after the Covid-19 pandemic, the continued development and introduction of used clothing products through this channel should be promoted more. Selling online requires a picture of the product, pricing the product followed by posting photos and prices, and adding a little bit of information about the product such as name, material, new price, current condition, etc.

*** Stores and business units of this item also need to strengthen Digital Marketing measures to better promote products, and create distribution channels for products, especially online channels.**

Or, **external factors** influence the decision to buy secondhand clothes with the factor **"Influenced by the uniqueness of the product"** and Camila Cozer's point of view (2018). According to the results of in-depth interviews, buyers 6 (NM6) and buyers 8 (NM8) also mentioned the uniqueness of the product as a decisive factor when buying secondhand goods. But buyers are also concerned with the problem of size selection as pointed out by Hiller Connell, K. Y. (2010), and the issue of product authenticity mentioned by Boardman, R., Zhou, Y., Guo, Y. (2022). Buyers of 8 (NM8) in the in-depth interview also agreed about the difficulty in choosing the size of clothes when saying: *"...I often buy clothes online, so there is no place to try and not check. product is. Many times, I was worn tight or the quality of the shirt was not what I wanted when I received it..."* Buyer 6 (NM6) was concerned about the authenticity when saying that *"...I see some shops mixing imported sources of different clothes and say incorrectly about the origin of the product. For example, a Lao or Cambodian T-shirt but says it's an American t-shirt..."*. According to the results of our in-depth interview, seller 1 (NB1) also agrees with this opinion, saying that *"...On our store's Instagram channel, we often use feedback images of some friends. bought from the store to promote..."*. In addition, buyers are concerned about wasting time choosing products every time they buy secondhand goods, which is consistent with the view made by Hur (2020). According to the interview results, buyers of 7 (NM7) and buyers of 8 (NM8) both said that hunting for stupid items takes a lot of time.

*** Seller needs to take pictures of the product if selling online. Note that if you want to create trust with customers, sellers should take real photos of the product, and avoid taking samples available online so customers will be more assured even if the clothes sold are second-hand. Sellers should choose a place with a beautiful background, and deep color to highlight the clothes.**

The research results also noted that the issue that consumers are most concerned about when choosing to buy secondhand clothes is "**Product quality**". The results of the in-depth interview with buyer 1 (NM1) also show this, when NM1 said that "...I am very interested in the brand of the product when buying secondhand. I will usually choose the item that is a brand name or a branded item instead of no-brand products...". In addition, it is necessary to show buyers more clearly the benefits that secondhand clothing products bring. Some of the benefits noted in the in-depth interview (NM6) are sustainability and cost savings, environmental friendliness (NM7), and fashion style issues (NM8&NM9).

Conclusion

It can be seen that the use of secondhand clothes is becoming a fashion trend for Vietnamese youth. However, young Vietnamese are still using these products at a normal level and have many concerns with them. To further develop the popularity of secondhand clothes among young people, sellers need to implement reasonable marketing methods and focus on addressing consumer concerns.

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